

Agro - Tourism: A New Era Of Rural Employment

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Abstract:

The Indian agriculture history is a long and rich from the ancient period. It is believed that agriculture start in India around 9 thousand BCE, with the cultivation of food grains and domestication of animals. Indian agriculture has evolved significantly, with the development of new techniques and technologies with eco-friendly system. Now days India is one of the world's largest producers of agricultural grains and agriculture continues to play a vital role in the country's economy progression. In this research paper studied about the journey of agriculture from as a producer to the tourism. This paper is explaining about the new era related to the agro- tourism in upcoming India. The agriculture is also use to be a tourist point of view. Indian farmers can generate additional income source beyond traditional agricultural practices, enhancing their livelihoods and contributing to the development of rural communities. Agro tourism helps maintain traditional farming system, down to earth knowledge and cultural heritage, ensuring their transmission to future generations. Agro tourism can promote increasing employment opportunities, sustainable practices, minimize environmental impacts and support local economies while preserving natural resources. However, challenges such as seasonality, lack of awareness, lack of regulations, competition from other forms of tourism and the need for careful planning and management must be addressed to ensure the long-term success and sustainability of agro tourism initiatives.

Keywords: Environmental Awareness, Agro-tourism, Inclusive Growth, Eco-friendly Product, Sustainable Development

Introduction:

“Empower villages, empower India” as per this thought after the independence, India has made significant progress in agricultural and industrial sector development. During the 5th five year plan Indian agriculture introduced of new technologies and the implementation of various government programs. Now day's Indian agriculture is facing a number of challenges, like climate change, soil degradation and scarcity of water and excess use of chemicals through fertilizers. The country

continues to be a major producer of agricultural products, and the government is taking steps against to the challenges of agriculture and made the agriculture as a tourist level. Agro-tourism, also known as farm tourism or rural tourism, agro tourism, is a form of commercial enterprise that combines agricultural production or processing with tourism to attract visitors to a farm. The visitors are also attracting to the ranch, agricultural business, processing units etc for entertainment or educational purposes.

Objective of the Study:

To study the role of Agro-tourism in Indian Economic Development.

Methodology:

The present study is based on secondary data published by the various research journal articles, websites, books etc.

Factors of Agro-tourism

Following are some key factors that influence the success of agro tourism in India.

A) Farm Resources for Attractions:

1. The use of unique Features: In the farm need to use special crops, livestock, plant attractive trees, scenic views, historical structures etc.
2. Organize Activities: The agro tourism will success if there is organize farm tours, farm-to-table dining, U-pick experiences (fruits, vegetables), animal encounters, workshops (cheese making, winemaking), festivals for children's, swimming pools etc.
3. Educational programs: Visitors learn about agricultural practices, such as crop cultivation, animal husbandry, soil testing, water testing, mixed crops and food production.
4. Accommodation facility: The visitors are interested if there is a farm stays facility available, cottages, glamping options.

B) Market related Factors:

1. Target Audience: Create curiosity in the audience to visit the specific demographics (families, couples, foodies, nature lovers)
2. Aware about Competition: Understanding the agro tourism

competitors in the region. And need to the changes as per the demands.

3. Health awareness: At the farm site arrange healthy food for adults and children's.
4. Direct-to-consumer sales: Visitors purchase agricultural products like, milk, fruit juice, vegetables, directly from farmers.

C) Environmental and Community Factors:

1. Support of Local agencies: Collaboration with other local agencies, complementary businesses, community involvement.
2. Sustainability: Eco-friendly practices, preserving natural resources.
3. Cultural Significance: Showcasing local traditions and heritage in the form of different types of images, statues.

D) Government Support:

1. Funding & Incentives: The governments are motivates to the farmers to create such tourism in the form of grants, tax breaks, loans.
2. Infrastructure facilities: Improved roads, available clean water and internet access, etc.
3. Policy & Regulations: Creating a favorable environment for agro tourism businesses at village levels.

Benefits of Agro-tourism:

1. **Increase in income:** Agro-tourism provides a supplementary source of income for the village farmers, which are not earning so far from the traditional agriculture. This one is helping to diversify their

operations and increase profitability.

2. **Preservation of agricultural heritage:** Agro-tourism helps to preserve traditional farming practices and rural lifestyles. It will motivate to the upcoming generations as a business.
3. **Economic development of rural areas:** Agro-tourism can stimulate economic growth in rural communities by attracting tourists and creating jobs. The Indian farmer's offers job to the agriculture graduates in their farm through the agro tourism.
4. **Educational opportunities:** Agro-tourism provides visitors with a unique opportunity to learning by doing about modern agriculture and connects with nature.
5. **Sustainable tourism:** Agro-tourism can promote sustainable tourism practices by minimizing environmental impact with use of natural resources with the supporting local communities.
6. **Job creation:** Create a new employment opportunities in hospitalities, tourism and dependent sectors
7. **Preservation of agriculture land:** Agro tourism is making farming economically viable, eco-friendly. It gives protection to the land from the chemicals. It will only uses a natural fertilizers to increase productions.

Overall, agro-tourism is a valuable form of tourism that benefits both farmers and visitors, while promoting the preservation of agricultural heritage and the sustainable development of rural India.

By following these above steps, farmers can successfully develop and operate a thriving agro tourism business at their local level. Provide unique and rewarding experiences for visitors while generating additional income for their farms also.

Challenges of Agro Tourism:

Agro tourism, while offering numerous benefits to the farmers, also presents several following challenges:

1. **Seasonality:** Many agricultural activities are seasonal, leading to fluctuations in visitor numbers and revenue throughout the year. In many of the area is depend on the monsoon. So the challenge in front of farmers to keep greenery over the year. All the resources are not available at needy places, so this one is totally depended on the nature. When overcome this challenge making artificial well to conserve water. Due to these facilities the expenditure will increases.
2. **Competition:** In Agro tourism businesses face competition from other tourist destinations and entertainment options given

by the competitors. Visitors are comparing the charges of agro tourism with other seasonable tourisms.

3. **Marketing & Promotion:** Effectively reaching target audiences and promoting agro tourism experiences can be challenging and costly. This business need awareness in the society then the target groups will accept the tourist point.
4. **Customer service:** The agro tourism business needs the actions on the feedback of the visitors in the form of customer service. This is the one of the main challenge on the development of agro tourism.
5. **Making branding:** In the development competition it is so hard to make a brand in the markets. Because the other businesses are lower prices offering to the visitors compare to this business, due to the higher cost in this business take a long time to make a brand.
6. **Regulations:** The agro tourism needs the local government support through the regulations. These regulations are guidelines for the visitors as well as the farmers who want to start this type of businesses.
7. **Labour Shortages:** The unemployment rate is high in our country. But still for these business labours are not available.

Agro tourism needs the skilled labour but the trained and qualified staffs are not available.

Agro tourism presents a unique opportunity for a mutually beneficial relationship between the agricultural and tourism sectors to the farmers. By offering visitors immersive experiences in rural settings, agro tourism provides a valuable platform. Farmers can generate additional income streams beyond traditional agricultural practices, enhancing their livelihoods and contributing to the revitalization of rural communities.

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